

Health

CHAMPIONING A NEW ERA OF DIGITAL HEALTH THROUGH COLLABORATION, COOPERATION AND CHANGE, (UN SDG #3, Good Health and Wellbeing)

Policy need to embrace “all-of-government” and cross ecosystem approach which incentivizes all participants in healthcare to improve essential health services at all stages of the life through investment in digital and data strategies by:

- ◆ Enabling universal access to integrated shared health records.
- ◆ Move to an outcome based healthcare model integrating high quality data.
- ◆ Allocate financial and regulatory resources towards achieving digital transformation.
- ◆ Enable, educate and Empower Patients to help them excel
- ◆ Use technology to provide better, more balanced and sustainable careers for health workers

Introduction

The Manhattan Manifesto has been prepared following the second digital health symposium at the United Nations General Assembly 77 Science Summit in New York, which was held on the 26th & 27th September 2022.

This Manhattan Manifesto for digital health provides a dozen principles which are recommended as guidance for policy makers, digital health strategists and implementation teams, health care professionals and most importantly for people.

The manifesto is tight on principles and tight on measurement which can be used as a guide to inform actions in different regions. Of necessity, implementation actions will be different in the various regions across the world.

Guidelines to Digital Health in a New Era

- ◆ People at the center. Empower people, their families and communities to achieve health and wellness.
- ◆ Health is “Whealth” – Healthcare is an essential contributor to economic wellbeing & growth.
- ◆ Recognize and address the unique challenge faced by women and girls in accessing health care.
- ◆ Seek Government commitment to allocate 6% of public healthcare spending to digital health.
- ◆ Provide leadership through a national digital health body that is outcomes-orientated.
- ◆ Embrace the [Health Data Governance Principles](#) as a step towards global standards.
- ◆ Be agile. Be rapid. Drive the step change.
- ◆ Align funding instruments supporting value-based healthcare for people, communities and population.
- ◆ Improve access to globally available data to provide evidence for personalized healthcare.
- ◆ Utilize digital technology and data to improve the quality of acute care and reduce harm.
- ◆ Drive towards eliminating disparities in healthcare delivery and inequity in outcomes.
- ◆ Embrace justice.

Why Is This Important?

Everyone deserves quality healthcare to achieve wellness. Our current model is no longer affordable or effective. We live in an age of constraints – our populations are older, our fiscal headroom is tighter, our workforce is more mobile than ever before. This model of “doctors and institutions” is no longer fit for purpose and calls for a new approach to healthcare.

Governments need healthy populations able to work beyond the age of 65. To achieve this, we need to shift care out of hospitals and into the community. Shift care closer to home (shift-left). Global healthcare research supports integrated health and social care in the community that is flexible, personalised, and seamless. A personal, digital platform that systematically collects and integrates high quality data, is a critical enabler for this vision of longer and healthier lives for all.

How does digital self-care improve daily life? Individuals can access online education, integrated personal health records, and accessible guidelines, made available through multiple channels of support, providing care and advice in a timely manner. These mediums reduce inequity and increase healthcare, ultimately improving workforce productivity.

By leveraging this data, and emerging technologies, healthcare systems will be able to rapidly identify effective responses for individuals and populations. Individuals will experience cutting-edge health information daily, with the immediate implementation of new evidence.

This allows for individuals and their governments to build trust in one another, igniting a virtuous cycle of fuller lives and thriving communities, that rewards achievements towards digital health and wellness outcomes. Governments that empower leadership and strive to build trusted relationships, embrace the Health Data Governance Principles, and put the necessary organizations in place to transparently achieve and maintain these guidelines. They invest in digital healthcare that will transform their health and social care systems while enhancing policy goals and implementing just systems. We argue that “Health is Wealth” and in this set of guidelines and proposals we set forth how policymakers can create healthier, wealthier, and happier societies, where equity of access and equal possibility of wellness is the core feature.

List of Attendees: UNGA77 Science Summit Digital Health Symposium Global Digital Health Leadership Steering Group (GDHLSG)

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